

Assessment Vitality of the Ovum by Natural Pigments Compares with Trypan Blue

Mudhafar Abdulhussein M. Al-Khudhory

Faculty of Medicine, Jabir Ibn Hayyan University for Medical and Pharmaceutical Sciences, Iraq

Abstract

Trypan blue is a pigment derived from toluidine. It is used to assess oocyte vitality by staining non-viable oocytes blue and leaving viable oocytes unstained. It stains dead oocytes by penetrating the cell membrane and entering the cytoplasm, but cannot do so in viable oocytes. Other pigments can be extracted from plants such as berries or beetroot. These plants can produce natural pigments which can be used for various purposes. The fruit of the mulberry tree is used in a wide range of medical fields. Several phytochemicals were found in berries, such as anthocyanins, epicatechin and chlorogenic acid. Berries contain a variety of antioxidant compounds that may protect the cellular system from oxidative damage. On the other hand, beetroot is a bulbous root similar to a tuber. It consists of multiple biologically active phytochemicals. Beetroot can provide natural red colouring when boiled. The red colour of beetroot is produced by the red betacyanin pigment. Beetroot is a rich natural source of antioxidants. It is one of the most important plants in terms of antioxidant activity. In this study, different plant pigments were used to evaluate the vitality of oocytes.

Keywords: *Infertility, oocyte, oocyte viability, khudhory red pigment, new pigment, trypan blue, berries, beetroot.*

Suggested citation: Al-Khudhory, M.A.M. (2026). Assessment Vitality of the Ovum by Natural Pigments Compares with Trypan Blue. *Scientia. Technology, Science and Society*, 3(1), 1-10. DOI: 10.59324/stss.2026.3(2).01

Abbreviations

NS: normal saline

SMART: simple medium for assisted reproductive technique

COCs: cumulus-oocytes complexes

BSA: bovine serum albumin

+CC: present cumulus cells

-CC: absent cumulus cells

Introduction

Trypan blue is a pigment derived from toluidine. Also known as diamine blue or Niagara blue, it was first used in 1904. It is used to assess oocyte vitality by staining non-viable oocytes blue and leaving viable oocytes unstained (Sousa et al., 2014). Trypan blue stains dead oocytes by penetrating the cell membrane via pores in the membrane and entering the cytoplasm of non-viable oocytes.

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However, in viable oocytes, the cell membrane is intact and trypan blue cannot penetrate it (Sousa et al., 2014). Other pigments can be extracted from the plants and used for similar purposes. Several plants, including berries and beetroot, can produce natural pigments when their juice is extracted. These pigments can be used for various purposes.

Many species of berries, such as the mulberry (*Morus rubra* L.), black chokeberry (*Aronia melanocarpa*), blueberry (*Vaccinium corymbosum*), cranberry (*Vaccinium macrocarpon*) and blackberry (*Rubus caesius*) (Kim, 2018) contain natural pigments. Mulberry is used in a wide range of medical field (Liu, 2003). Several phytochemicals are found in the berries, including anthocyanins, epicatechin and chlorogenic acid (Sui et al., 2016).

Berries contain a wide variety of antioxidant compounds (Prior et al., 1998) including flavonoids, phenolic acids and anthocyanine (Soobrattee et al., 2005), that may help protect cellular system from oxidative damage (Prior et al., 1998). Phenolic components have many useful effects in the treatment of a multitude disease (Soobrattee et al., 2005). Phenolic compounds (in terms of their biological activities) are considered to contribute to the anti-inflammatory, anti-carcinogenic, anti-angiogenic and antioxidant properties of berries (Clifford, 2000; Kong et al., 2003; Rossi et al., 2003).

Many studies on berries have proven that they have an in vitro antioxidant activity (Szymanowska et al., 2018; Fidelis et al., 2020; Rodrigues et al., 2020; Skenderidis et al., 2018; Ribera-Fonseca et al., 2020), such as chelation of transition metal ions, H⁺ ion transfer and electron transfer (Azman et al., 2020; Moraes et al., 2020; Rodrigues et al., 2020). Many species of anthocyanins are found in berries including delphinidin, petunidin, pelargonidin, malvidin, cyaniding and peonidin. Extracts of the anthocyanins display a wide range of biological activities such as antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial (Ramos, 2008).

Beetroot, also known as red beetroot, is a bulbous root similar to a tuber (Setiawan, 1995). It consists of multiple biologically active phytochemicals (Baião et al., 2017). Beetroot can provide natural red colouring when boiled. The red colour of beetroot is produced by red betacyanin and yellow betaxanthin pigments (groups of pigments known as betalains or betanins) (Anam et al., 2013).

Beetroot is a rich source of natural antioxidants and has anti-cancer, anti-inflammatory (Anam et al., 2013), anti-diabetic and anti-carcinogenic properties (Clifford et al., 2015). Beetroot is considered one of the plants with the highest antioxidant activity (Baião et al., 2017). It also contains many minerals, including magnesium, manganese, potassium, sodium, calcium, phosphorus and zinc. It also contains copper, which is important for human health and plays a role in metabolism (Petek et al., 2019). Beetroot contains iron, which is useful for pregnant women (Bobek et al., 2000).

In this study, trypan blue was used alongside some plant juices (from berries and beetroot) to assess the vitality of oocytes, as an alternative to trypan blue.

Materials and Methods

Ovaries Collection

After collecting the ovaries from a local abattoir, they are transplanted to the laboratory in a container containing normal saline (NS) at 37°C for 40 minutes (see Figure 1). Using a 10 mL syringe with a 23-gauge needle, separate the contents of the follicles on the surface of the ovaries, including the oocytes. Then, the oocytes were washed three times with SMART medium

(Fakhrildin & Flayyih, 2009). Then incubate in SMART medium at 37°C. This study used cumulus-oocyte complexes (COCs) with homogeneous cytoplasm.

Figure 1. A Group of Animal Ovaries

Aspiration of Oocytes

For aspiration, the follicular contents of the ovaries (including the oocyte and fluid) are collected from the surface of the ovaries using a disposable, sterile 10 mL syringe fitted with a 23-gauge hypodermic needle. The follicular contents of the ovaries are aspirated using the technique shown in Figure 2, from all the visible follicles on the surface of the ovaries with a diameter of approximately 4-6 mm. The syringe contains a solution of 20 IU/ml heparin, 5% BSA and 0.5 ml SMART medium. Then, transfer all of the contents of the syringe into a Petri dish. Examine the contents under a dissecting microscope and collect the oocytes from the fluid using an automatic micropipette or a modified Pasteur pipette. Then, wash twice with SMART medium (see Figure 3). Incubate in SMART medium at 37°C.

Figure 2. Separation of Oocytes from Ovaries

Figure 3. Retrieved Oocytes

Preparation of Trypan Blue

To prepare the trypan blue stain, dissolve 0.2 g of trypan blue powder in 50 ml of normal saline. Then filter the stain using filter paper. Then store it in a dark bottle in the refrigerator. Trypan blue

is used to differentiate between viable and non-viable oocytes before natural pigments are used for evaluation purposes.

Preparation of khudhory Red (Mulberry Stain)

Prepared according to a procedure invented by Dr. Mudhafar Abdulhussein (Al-Khudhory, 2025).

Preparation of Beta Vulgaris (Beetroot) Stain

Collection of beetroot from the market and washing it very well to remove any plankton from them, then the beetroot are cut and placed with water in a container to boil at (100 C⁰) for 30 minutes, where the extract is with moderate textures, neither light nor thick, leave the mixture to cool, after that remove pieces of beetroot and the extract is taken to put in tube. At the end, filtration the extract with filter paper, last put in the dark bottle in the refrigerator.

Viability Test

Firstly, the vitality of all oocytes was examined using trypan blue to classify them as either non-viable (dead) oocytes (fully stained) or viable (live) oocytes (unstained) (see Figures 4 and 5). Then, the non-viable oocytes were removed. The viable oocytes were divided into two groups. In the first group, the Khudhory red (mulberry stain) was used to evaluate the oocytes' viability, and in the second group, the beta vulgaris pigment was used to evaluate the oocytes' viability. In both groups, the oocytes were unstained. After this, all oocytes in both groups were left to die by leaving them outside the incubator in a nutrient-free medium for a long time or in unsuitable temperature conditions (high/low). Finally, the assessment of viability was repeated using khudhory red and beta vulgaris pigments.

Figure 4. Non-Viable Oocyte

Figure 5. Viable Oocyte

Results and Discussion

In this study, 110 ovaries were obtained from a local slaughterhouse and 228 oocytes were separated. The highest and lowest numbers of recuperated oocytes were 30 and 15, respectively. The highest number of immature oocytes recovered was 20, with a percentage of 66.66%, while the lowest number of immature oocytes recovered was nine, with a percentage of 60%. The highest number of recovered mature oocytes was 10, with a percentage of 41.66%, while the lowest number

was 3, with a percentage of 20%. Also, the highest number of recovered atretic oocytes was 4, with a percentage of 13.33%, and the lowest number was 0, with a percentage of 0% (see Table 1).

Most of the oocytes obtained were immature, with a few mature. Of the 228 recuperated oocytes, 145 were immature, 69 were mature and 14 were atretic. All of these oocytes were obtained from 110 ovaries (see Table 1).

Table 1. Number of Recovered Oocytes and Ovaries and Oocytes Classification

NO. of aspiration	NO. of ovaries	NO. of oocytes	Oocytes classification					
			mature		immature		atretic	
			NO.	%	NO.	%	NO.	%
1	10	24	7	29.16	16	66.66	1	4.16
2	12	24	10	41.66	12	50	2	8.33
3	8	20	8	40	11	55	1	5
4	8	15	5	33.33	9	60	1	6.66
5	10	16	5	31.25	11	68.75	-	-
6	12	20	8	40	10	50	2	10
7	6	15	3	20	11	73.33	1	6.66
8	10	24	8	33.33	14	58.33	2	8.33
9	7	20	5	25	15	75	-	-
10	13	20	4	20	16	80	-	-
11	14	30	6	20	20	66.66	4	13.33
Total and mean	110	228	69	30.26	145	63.59	14	6.14

During this work, the oocytes were classified according to the presence or absence of cumulus cells. The total number of oocytes recovered with cumulus cells was greater than the number of oocytes recovered without cumulus cells (see Figure 6).

Figure 6. Oocytes with Presence or Absence of Cumulus Cells

The first step in this work is to evaluate the viability of the oocytes using trypan blue. Usually, dead (non-viable) oocytes turn blue when stained with trypan blue, whereas live (viable) oocytes do not (Sousa et al., 2014). Trypan blue penetrates the cell membrane of a dead oocyte, passing through the pores into the cytoplasm and colouring it blue. In a live oocyte, however, the cell membrane and cytoplasm cannot be penetrated by trypan blue, so the oocyte does not acquire the blue colour

(Sudha & Reddy, 2013). Therefore, all blue oocytes were non-viable, while non-blue oocytes were viable. After collecting and preparing the oocytes in the laboratory, examine the viability of all oocytes using trypan blue to remove the non-viable oocytes (fully stained, see Figure 7) and retain the viable oocytes (unstained, see Figure 8) for the next step. Then, the viable oocytes were divided into two groups: group 1 (G1) used the red stain (Khudhory red) and group 2 (G2) used the beetroot pigment.

Figure 7. Non-Viable Oocyte (Dead) after Trypan Blue

Figure 8. Viable Oocyte (Live) after Trypan Blue

In group 1 (G1), two to three drops of khudhory red were added to the viable oocytes and left for one minute before examination. Not all oocytes were stained, which means that they are viable (see figure 9). Then, leave the viable oocytes under unsuitable conditions, such as outside the incubator at a temperature of more or less 37°C, to die. In the final step, use khudhory red again to evaluate viability. Most of the oocytes acquired the red colour, indicating the presence of khudhory red. This indicates that they are dead (non-viable) (Al-Khudhory, 2025) (see Figure 10). To confirm this, use trypan blue to stain the oocytes; this indicates that they are dead.

Figure 9. Viable Oocyte (Live) after Khudhory Red

Figure 10. Non-Viable Oocyte (Dead) after Khudhory Red

In group 2 (G2), two to three drops of beetroot stain were added to the viable oocytes and left for two minutes before examination. Not all of the oocytes were stained, which means that they are viable. Then, leave the viable oocytes under unsuitable conditions to die. After that, use the beetroot stain again to evaluate the viability. It was found that none of the oocytes acquired any colour, indicating that the beetroot stain did not penetrate the cell membrane or enter the oocyte, even if it was a dead cell (see Figure 11). To confirm this, we used trypan blue: the oocytes stained with the dye, indicating that they were dead. Therefore, the beetroot stain is not useful for evaluating the viability of oocytes.

Figure 11. Oocyte without Dye after Beetroot Stain

Conclusion

This study concluded that the khudhory red pigment (mulberry stain) could be used to evaluate the vitality of oocytes, whereas the beetroot stain could not. New pigments were successfully prepared and tested.

Ethics Statement

This study was conducted following ethical guidelines established by the Ministry of Higher Education and Scientific Research in Iraq for research involving animal subjects. All procedures were carried out to minimize discomfort and ensure humane treatment of the animals. The author declares no conflicts of interest related to this study.

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